

Studies on the Flavanones of *Leucaena glauca* Benth.

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Leucaena glauca (family : Mimosaceae) is a large shrub with light yellow globose head inflorescences. The leaves are used as fodder for milching cattle. The plant is rich in selenium and used in traditional medicine¹. Isolation of flavonols like quercetagenin and patuletin from the plant has been reported². With a view to locating further flavanone in *L. glauca*, we undertook investigation of its fresh inflorescences and the results are reported here.

The fresh inflorescences of *L. glauca* (1 kg) (collected from Kanagappapuram, Kanyakumari district, S. India in October) were extracted with boiling ethanol and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue from the ethanolic extract was successively fractionated with petroleum ether, peroxide-free Et₂O and EtOAc. The residue from ethereal fraction on crystallisation from MeOH afforded pale cream coloured leaflets (1; 50 mg), m.p. 245°. It was identified as hesperetin by m.p., m.m.p., PC and uv data with an authentic sample isolated from *Asclepias curassavica*³. The EtOAc fraction was concentrated and the residue on column chromatography over silica gel, on elution with acetone afforded a yellow solid (2; 160 mg), m.p. 248°, λ_{\max} (MeOH) 283, 326; +NaOMe 242, 286, 318, 356; +AlCl₃ 308, 383; +AlCl₃-HCl 306, 379; +NaOAc 284, 328; +NaOAc-H₃BO₃ 284, 326 nm; ¹H nmr δ (270 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 5.43 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-6), 6.14 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.96 (3H, s, H-2', H-5' and H-6'), 4.99 (1H, q, *J*_{cis} 5 Hz, *J*_{trans} 11 Hz, H-2), 2.80 (2H, m, H-3), 3.81 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 9.12 (1H, s, 3'-OH), 12.03 (1H, s, 5-OH), 4.50 (gluc H-1''), 4.65 (rhamn H-1'''), 0.90 (rhamn-Me); ¹³C nmr δ (100.61 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 78.4 (C-2), 42.1 (C-3), 197.0 (C-4), 163.1 (C-5), 96.5 (C-6), 165.2 (C-7), 95.7 (C-8), 162.6 (C-9), 103.4 (C-10), 131.0 (C-1'), 114.2 (C-2'), 146.5 (C-3'), 148.1 (C-4'), 112.1 (C-5'), 117.9 (C-6'), 55.8 (C of O-CH₃), 99.6 (C-1''), 73.1 (C-2''), 76.4 (C-3''), 70.8 (C-4''), 75.6 (C-5''), 66.1 (C-6''), 100.7 (C-1'''), 70.4 (C-2'''), 69.7 (C-3'''), 72.2 (C-4'''), 68.4 (C-5'''), 17.9 (C-6''').

Compound 2 responded to the Gibb's⁴, Molisch's and cyanidin⁵ tests but did not respond to the H \ddot{o} rhammer-Hansel⁶ and Wilson's boric acid⁷ tests. The characteristic colour reactions and spectral properties indicated 2 to be a flavanone glycoside. It was hydrolysed (5% H₂SO₄, 100°, 2 h) to hesperetin, glucose and rhamnose. The aglycone and the sugars were identified by co-chromatography on

paper. The site of glycosidation at C-7 was apparent from the absence of a bathochromic shift in band-II of uv-spectrum of the glycoside 2 on addition of NaOAc, whereas the aglycone showed a bathochromic shift of 35 nm. In ¹³C nmr the downfield signals of C-6 and C-8 and the upfield signal of C-7 confirm the site of glycosidation at C-7⁸. Compound 2 was prone to hydrolysis with pectinase⁹ and it gave hesperetin 7-*O*-glucoside on partial hydrolysis with 10% formic acid in cyclohexanol¹⁰. These facts indicated the biose to be rutinose (α -L-rhamno-(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -D-glucose) which was confirmed by the appearance of ¹H nmr signal of methyl protons of rhamnose¹¹ at δ 0.90 and ¹³C nmr signals of C-6''' of rhamnose at 17.9 ppm and that of C-6'' of glucose at 66.1 ppm¹². Compound 2 was thus identified as hesperetin-7-*O*-rutinoside (hesperidin).

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